

CEDEFOP

European Centre for the Development
of Vocational Training

50
YEARS
SHAPING LEARNING AND
SKILLS IN EUROPE

Cedefop's European skills and jobs survey

Strengthening skills intelligence for Europe

CEDEFOP

European Centre
for the Development
of Vocational Training

European
skills & jobs
survey

Cedefop surveys make it possible to analyse **jobs and skills mismatch from various angles**

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Second European skills and jobs survey

Digitalisation and skill mismatch

Main research questions:

- What do EU workers do at work?
- Basic or complex(digital) skills use?
- New digital technologies?
- Skill gaps and remedial learning?

Better measurement of:

- Job-skill requirements
- Digitalisation/digital work
- (Digital) skills complexity
- Work organisation
- Skill mismatches / training

Pillars and conceptual design

Survey development

Factual questions

Explicit scaling

Generalisable

Common-objective scales

Discrete responses

Short time window

Minimal prospective Q's

Job as reference

Expert group

Extensive pre-testing

High quality translation

Robust fieldwork

EUROPEAN SKILLS & JOBS SURVEY

ESJS2 survey ID

SURVEY METHOD

RDD CATI

Weighting

ONLINE (CAWI)

PSM

COUNTRIES SURVEYED

EU-27
+ Iceland
+ Norway

TARGET NUMBER OF INTERVIEWS

Ranging from 1 000 to 3 000 –
total of **46 213 observations**.
500 by RDD CATI
(except 1000 in MT, CY)

TARGET POPULATION

All adults (aged 25-64) in
wage and salary employment
(i.e. paid employees, excluding
self-employment and family
workers), who live in private
households

DURATION

About 20-25 min

ESJS2 note of caution

- Mixed mode (CATI-CAWI) sampling (PSM, weighting)
- Some variables only in online sample
- Small country sample sizes
- Digitalisation – ‘major’ changes
- Digital activities – not DigComp approach
- Skill mismatch – subjective
- Only task – not job - automation

ESJS2 online tool

29
countries
EU-27 plus
Norway and
Iceland

46 213
EU+
adult workers

**Representative
data**
of EU+
labour markets

**More
than
80**
indicators

COMPARATIVE EU+ INFORMATION ON

- Skill demands
- Work organisation
- Remote work
- Digitalisation and automation
- Skill gaps and mismatch
- Training and learning for work
- Covid-19 pandemic impact

<https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/tools/european-skills-jobs-survey>

ESJS2

research and policy analysis

[Challenging digital myths](#)

[Setting Europe on course for a human digital transition](#)

[Untangling labour shortages in Europe: unmet skill demand or bad jobs?](#)

VET needs to go digital: Upgrading the backbone of Europe's twin transition

[What drives workers' participation in digital skills training? Evidence from Cedefop's second European skills and jobs survey \(JRC-Cedefop\)](#)

Divergent or convergent? Gaps in skilled work between EU and Western Balkans (*ETF-Cedefop*)

Under review

- Human-centred technological change?
Using skills as an agent for change
- Are AI skills a reward or a gamble?
Deconstructing the AI wage premium in Europe

Human-centred technological change?

- We identify a latent categorical variable representing technology-job design worker profiles.
- We use #ESJS2 information on:
 - Digital skill needs
 - Foundation (literacy, numeracy) skill needs
 - Job complexity
- We examine the relationship between technology-job design profiles and labour market outcomes:
 - Job satisfaction
 - Hourly wage
 - Automation expectations

Technology complements skills, but digital transition needs to be well-managed

Variables	(1) Job satisfaction	(2) Fear of being displaced	(3) Hourly wage (ln)
Profile 1	0 (.)	0 (.)	0 (.)
Profile 2	0.00988 (0.24)	0.268*** (5.43)	0.0305** (2.68)
Profile 3	-0.0179 (-0.37)	0.346*** (6.52)	0.101*** (6.27)
Wages			
Under lowest quartile	0 (.)		
Between lowest quartile and median	-0.00900 (-0.09)		
Between median and highest quartile	0.158 (1.30)		
Above highest quartile	0.394** (3.09)		
New digital technologies	-0.0910** (-3.04)	0.0452* (1.98)	-0.000520 (-0.05)
More frequent use of dig. tech. due to Covid-19 pandemic	0.0249 (1.05)	0.281*** (10.51)	0.0578*** (7.19)
Skills utilisation (great extent)	0.312*** (12.19)	-0.156*** (-4.43)	0.0364*** (4.50)
Satisfaction with relations with supervisors	0.325*** (23.92)	-0.0300*** (-6.55)	
Observations	28772		

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Demographic characteristics include: gender, age, quadratic age, highest level of education, required level of education, type of area.

Job characteristics include: hours worked, type of contract, firm size, private sector, tenure, remote work, new working methods.

NACE, ISCO, and country codes are also included.

AI skills wage premium

AI programmers are employed in **more diverse, new jobs** and with more **variable pay** than non-AI programmers.

4-8% higher wages than non-AI programmers.

12-24% higher wages than similarly educated workers.

Figure A1 Percentage contributions of predictors to the explained component

NB: OB decomposition of equation (1) using the log hourly wage as dependent variable and specification (4). The construction of the job complexity and job-skill requirements indices is described in Cedefop (2024a). The detailed decomposition is subsumed by sets of covariates. *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$; Robust standard errors in parenthesis.

Source: Cedefop second European skills and jobs survey (ESJS2)

ESJS2 supplement

Artificial Intelligence

Cedefop AI skills survey (2024)

Conference outcomes

- **Cedefop working paper series** – conference proceedings
 - light editing
 - papers submitted by spring 2025
 - publication in Q3-4 2025
- **Journal of Education and Work** (eds. Craig Holmes, University of Oxford & Cedefop)
 - limited number of papers following peer-review
 - papers submitted by summer 2025
 - publication end of 2025 or early 2026

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